

Confinement in domestic horses

Social and movement needs of horses

Horses are gregarious animals. Under natural conditions, they live in groups with strong social bonds between conspecifics. They establish stable and long-term relationships, learn from each other, and show synchronised patterns of behavioural activity due to social facilitation. Under natural conditions, horses spend 50–75% of their day walking to find food, water or shelter. When housed in individual boxes, horses are motivated to access a paddock, and are even more motivated when conspecifics are present in that paddock.

Horses are often housed in individual boxes to individualise feeding and to limit the risk of injuries caused by conspecifics. Prolonged confinement in individual boxes can have a negative impact on horse welfare, especially when there is no turn-out to paddocks and no contact with conspecifics.

Legal requirements

Directive 98/58/EC on the protection of animals kept for farming purposes states that:

'The freedom of movement of an animal, having regard to its species and in accordance with established experience and scientific knowledge, must not be restricted in such a way as to cause it unnecessary suffering or injury. Where an animal is continuously or regularly tethered or confined, it must be given the space appropriate to its physiological and ethological needs in accordance with established experience and scientific knowledge.'

(Directive 98/58/EC, Annex, Point 7)

Method to assess the impact on welfare

The restriction of movement or of social contacts in horses have negative impacts on:

- Behaviour
- Physiology and health
- Cognition
- Trainability and safety (for horses and humans)

These impacts in turn affect horse welfare. Measures should be taken to enable freedom of movement and appropriate social contacts.

To know more, see the review '**Confinement, restriction of social contacts and movement in domestic horses**'.

For recommendations for inspection, please refer to the **Indicator factsheet 'Confinement in domestic horses'**.

Impact of confinement on horse welfare

The various impacts of restricting social contacts or movement on the welfare of horses are listed below (Table 1).

Table 1: Impacts on behaviour, physiology and health, cognition and trainability of restricting social contacts and movement in horses. The impacts have been identified by comparing horses housed in individual boxes with no or limited access to paddock/pasture to horses vs. horses grouped at pasture.

Impacts of restricting social contacts and movement in horses	
Behaviour	Stereotypies (e.g. crib-biting ¹ , weaving ² , pacing ³)
	Aggressiveness towards humans
	Changes in lying behaviour (decrease or increase in time spent lying down)
	Decrease in forage intake
	Increase in emotional reactivity (stress) towards a novel object
Physiology and health	Increase in the frequency of vigilance postures
	Changes in heart rate and heart rate variability (increase or decrease)
	Increase in stress hormone levels (cortisol) in blood and saliva and of its metabolites in faeces
	Decreased immune function
	<u>During weaning:</u>
	Biochemical changes (e.g. inadequate iron uptake, lower protein turnover)
	Lower bone mineral content
	Gastric inflammation and ulceration
	<u>Adult horses:</u> higher risk of:
	Skin lesions
Inflammation of the upper respiratory tract	
Limb oedema	
Stomach ulcers	
REM-sleep deprivation	
Colic	
Cognition	Lower learning performances
	Lower behavioural flexibility (e.g. lower readiness to change a previously successful behaviour)
	Pessimistic judgement bias suggesting negative affective states (e.g. avoidance of ambiguous situations)
Trainability and safety	More unwanted behaviours (e.g. kicking, biting) during training
	More reactive to novel stimuli
	Less relaxed during training, less responsive to handlers' cues, and more stress related behaviours, all making training more difficult

¹ The horse grasps a solid surface with its front teeth and pulls back, contracting the neck muscles and making a characteristic grunting noise.

² The horse repeatedly moves its head and neck from side to side, shifting its weight from one front leg to the other.

³ The horse paces around the boundaries of a confined area.

Legal requirements

The legal requirements referred to are based on EU legislation. National regulations in EU Member States may exceed these requirements.

Council Directive 98/58/EC

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(Annex, Point 7)

References

Lansade, L., Hartmann, E., Minero, M., & Ruet, A. (2024). Review - Confinement, restriction of social contacts and movement in domestic horses. *EURCAW Ruminants & Equines*. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13785436>